

COOPERATION FOR SUCCESS: THE ROLE OF COLLABORATION IN BOOSTING TEACHING QUALITY AND STUDENT ENGAGEMENT IN ADDIS ABABA'S PRIVATE SCHOOLS

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Abstract

The purpose of this article is to examine the existing cooperation among teachers, school directors, and parents in private schools located in Addis Ababa and its relationship to teaching effectiveness and students' attitudes. The study aims to explore how such collaborations operate, identify cultural factors, and determine the resources necessary for cooperation within educational institutions. A quantitative self-administered questionnaire was distributed to 350 teachers (175 male and 175 female) from 25 private schools in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. Participants responded to questions regarding their experiences with collaborative practices, access to professional development, and engagement of parents and community members. The survey results indicate a positive attitude towards collaborative practices, with respondents recognizing the structured approach to professional development and parental participation. However, concerns were noted regarding a lack of resources and the need for staff development. Cultural attitudes were found not to be a barrier, while school leadership emerged as having a significant influence on collaborative efforts. This study highlights the importance of fostering sustainable practices between institutions to enhance teaching standards and improve student performance. It suggests that school administrations should allocate more resources to collaborative initiatives, enhance professional development programs, and actively engage community members in collaborative efforts. This study contributes to the existing literature by presenting qualitative findings regarding collaboration in private schools in Addis Ababa. It emphasizes the necessity of involving the community and sharing information to strengthen cooperation among educational stakeholders, ultimately leading to a better learning climate for students.

Keywords: Collaboration, Impact, Teaching, Quality, Sustainable

1. INTRODUCTION

Sustainable collaboration in education fosters a dynamic environment where educators and students work together to enhance teaching quality and improve learning outcomes (Andriyani, et al., 2024; Bassachs, et al., 2020). Sustainable collaboration in context of education can also be described as long-term relationships between the key stakeholders of education teachers, administrators, parents and communities with the purpose of improving the educational process for learners (Penuel, et al., 2020). This contract involves granting respect, teaming up on agreeing objectives, appropriate and frequent communication, focusing on long-term partnership that assures interdependency for a compound learning atmosphere. In their capacity, stakeholders solve problems on an ongoing basis and provide support to facilitate student success (Chotimah, et al., 2024).

Why collaboration is important in education and a few of its benefits Cooperation is imperative in education for the following reasons (Dusdal, & Powell, 2021). It improves teaching quality by supporting educators in exchange of professional competence and practical processes that in turn better the strategies of teaching (Weddle, 2022). Moreover, collaboration helps students get more interested because of differentiated and unique activities created by teachers (Andriyani, et al., 2024). Besides academic education, it encourages friendly relations among students, friendly and emotional support that make children learn how to work in groups, share, and care for others (Ha, et al., 2024). Moreover, the approach engages families and the community as a means of support so that schools can facilitate the educational process and fill the gap between school and home environment (Sadrizadeh, et al., 2022).

Amidst these general observations, a new paradigm is emerging about Addis Ababa's private schools. These institutions have become popular as other forms of education, which are associated with better quality education than the public system (Alemayehu, 2021). Private schools have expanded partly due to the expanding need of education, perceived inadequacies within public sector schools, and a need for more extensive courses (Alemayehu, & Shibeshi 2021). These schools experience particular complexities and possibilities of sustainability as a collaboration (Haile, 2020). Having a diverse group of stakeholders including local and expatriate teachers and parents brings into the school both potential for increased creativity due to cultural diversity and conflict due to cultural difference and power structures (Assefa, 2022).

However, as this study reveals, there are serious challenges that negatively affect collaboration of many Addis Ababa's private schools. Lack of trust in the organization's structure can hinder free flowing communication within the organization especially when traditional structures promote authoritarianism, resource constraints can also hinder the advancement of collaborative projects (Deyasso, & Ashenafi, 2022). However, some schools are gradually wising up to the usefulness of long-term partnership and try out signs that can assist collaboration among workers, parents and the community (Al-Hail, et al., 2021).

Existing literature lacks extensive information on this subject, especially the flow of sustainable collaborative partnership in Addis Ababa's private schools. However, absent from the literature is a need for empirical investigations that have investigated the effectiveness of these collaborations on teaching effectiveness and students' achievements. Furthermore, it also would shed light on the documentation of best practices and the analysis of the cultural aspects that are relevant to collaboration. There must need be more longitudinal studies to give finer views on the dynamic of the process and identify possible development over time and the impact on the quality of education. The failure to fill these gaps will limit the advancement knowledge of sustainable collaboration in the Addis Ababa's private schools and its credence to enhancing the education system.

1.1 Purpose of the article

The purpose of this article is to explore the concept of sustainable collaboration within Ethiopian private schools and its impact on teaching quality and student outcomes. By examining both the mechanisms of collaboration and the experiences of various stakeholders, this article aims to provide insights into how these partnerships can enhance the educational landscape in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.

1.2 Basic research questions

The following are the three fundamental research questions that serve as the foundation for this article, guiding its exploration and analysis throughout the discussion. Each question aims to delve into different aspects of sustainable collaboration and its effects on teaching quality and student outcomes.

1) What collaborative practices are currently being implemented in Addis Ababa's private schools, and how do they vary among different institutions?

2) How does sustainable collaboration among teachers, administrators, and parents impact the quality of teaching and student engagement in Addis Ababa's private schools?

3) What are the key challenges and barriers to establishing sustainable collaboration in Addis Ababa's private schools, and how can these be addressed to enhance educational outcomes?

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1 Sustainability of co-operative management

For some time now, the concept of sustainable collaboration in education is considered one of the key success factors in enhancing teachers 'and or students' performance (Guerra, & Costa, 2021). It implies sustained relationships created through mutual planning, execution, evaluation, and reflection among various stakeholders' teacher, administrators, parents and the community in order to support the learning process (Teemant, et al., 2021). This supplement of work is defined by professionalism emphasizing cooperation reflecting the concept of community with common responsibilities (Kahila, et al., 2024). The results of the literature review indicate that not only does effective collaboration improve instruction but also it positively impacts advisement and student engagement (Nkomo, et al., 2021).

2.2 Roles of partnership in learning

The exclusion of those at educational settings has however attracted many concerns. Interdisciplinary model and collaboration between teachers involve several benefits including increased and enhanced practice in educating, high job morale, and reduced feelings of isolation (White, 2023). For example, teachers in collaborative professional development have increased knowledge on improved instructions and teachers' perceived training efficacy (Skae, 2023). Besides, cooperation enables more interest in students' work since individual interests are being applied when improving the teaching performance, thereby increasing the level of examination performance (Sarker, et al., 2024).

Teamwork is also paramount especially in the total development of the young people hence collaboration. In a study by Celume et al., (2020), the authors explain that students and adults learn socioemotional skills when they are in collaborative learning processes to foster bonding, sharing, team spirit, and Altruism. These skills are now considered as essential more and more in both academic and non-academic fields. Therefore, the promotion of collaboration within the school environment not only promotes the education achievements of students, but also equips them for future endeavors (Váradi, 2022).

2.3 Collaboration in the context of Ethiopian education

Several issues that characterize education in the horn of Africa, Ethiopia as it expands with many private

schools popping up as key options to the public schools (Tareke, et al., 2024). These institutions are usually deemed to offer quality education due to growing concerns with quality learning facilities and learning content (Antoninis, et al., 2023). Yet, nurturing the sustainable collaboration in private schools of Addis Ababa poses some difficulties and interesting prospects (Shkabatur, et al., 2022).

Denbi, (2019) argues that even though, private school in Addis Ababa can offer efficient collaboration practices, this is not easily achieved. Lack of interaction between stakeholders due to cultural barriers and dominance of traditional hierarchical systems are proved to be barriers to collaboration (Ganeshu, et al., 2023). Further, other challenges include issues to do with lack of adequate funding and, or training of teachers to facilitate implementation of the collaborative frameworks (Ní -Bhroin, & King, 2020).

2.4 Successful interorganizational processes

Many studies point out at specific practice that may help with collaborative collaboration in education. According to Carr, (2024), the professional learning communities (PLCs) to present a force for enhancing teaching practice. In PLCs teachers are able to discuss 'what works', problem solve communally, and access professional development continuously. Systematic integration of core gameplaying with other subject areas has been proved to enhance teacher credibility and learner accomplishment (Moon, et al., 2024).

Garcia, (2024) also stress the necessity to apply more formal forms of collaboration, for example, the use of peer-observation and peer-feedback. Their studies prove these practices to not only improve quality of teaching practice but also for cultural change or improvement among educators. Through setting the climate that allows the desktide observation of other teachers' classrooms lessons by provision of other teachers to observe, then schools should endeavor to make collaboration a foundation of professional development (Rachana, 2023).

2.5 Effects on dimensions such as teaching quality and student learning outcomes

According to the existing literature, collaboration contributes to enhanced student achievement. Karadag, (2020) meta-analysis of existing literature showed that effective collaborative culture within school corresponded with high effective learning achievement. This can be linked to teaching practices that are endowed by collaborative processes which are the major thrusts of this paper as they directly impact on the fortunes of the learners (Jain, et al., 2023).

Arguing in an assessment of Addis Ababa's private schools, Assefa (2022) showed that the schools adopting the collaborative practices highlighted the improvement in students' active participation and academic performances. Nonetheless, the findings emphasize the fact that in reality, efficacy of collaboration may greatly depend on the cultural and institutional specificities. These include the level of stakeholder involvement where different people have different abilities in terms of investment and the available resources meant for one's collaboration (Assefa, 2022).

2.6 Challenges to sustainable collaboration:

However, previous cross-sectional investigations showed that many private schools in Addis Ababa experience several barriers in achieving sustainable partnership (Melaku, & Addis, 2023). Lack of openness, restrictive communication and lack of collaboration of teachers and administrators might be hampered due to traditional hierarchical forms of organization structures as seen above (Saiti, & Stefou, 2020). This may lead to the culture of working aloof not a culture of working as a team and sharing responsibilities. Also, will limited access to resources and training of educators undermines collaborative endeavors (Weigele, 2019).

Another factor that posts significant impacts the essence of effective collaboration is cultural issues (Qureshi, et al., 2023). A number of the teachers may not be willing to discuss what they do in class or engage in collaborative professional learning. Lanning, (2022) argues that lack of willingness to share practice or gain ideas is instilled by fear or lack of trust in other teachers or other members of the school community. This emphasizes the need to develop organizational cultures in which people can share information, provide support where necessary and can learn from each other (Azeem, et al., 2021).

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research design

This study employed a quantitative methods approach to gain a comprehensive understanding of the challenges and barriers to establishing sustainable collaboration in Ethiopian private schools. The quantitative component involved the use of a Likert scale survey.

3.2 Participants

The target population for this study included teachers, administrators, and parents from 25 private schools across Ethiopia. A stratified random sampling technique was used to ensure representation from different regions and types of private schools (e.g., religious, international, and local schools). The sample aimed to include 350 teachers (175 male and 175 females), ensuring a balanced representation of stakeholders. Out of the twenty-five private

schools from each one 14 teachers i.e. 7 male and 7 females' teachers were randomly chosen.

3.3 Data collection

A structured survey was developed based on five Likert scale questions addressing key challenges to sustainable collaboration. The survey was distributed in paper format to accommodate participants' preferences. The survey items were designed to assess perceptions regarding cultural barriers, resource limitations, communication issues, leadership support, and the need for training.

3.4 Instrument validity and reliability

In the survey instrument used for the study, validity and reliability of the assessment was established. The Instrument used in this study had arbitrary response format which was a 5-point Likert scale. The validity of the survey validity was established through Content Validity whereby reliability of the survey instrument was established to ensure the items included in the survey were relevant and the measure is most directly an indication and representative of the construct being measured. The reliability of the survey instrument used was also checked. This was done through such practices of internal consistency reliability of the four proposed measures of internationalization. Cronbach's Alpha method was used to assess the Invalidated pronouns were used occasionally in the study on the internal structure of the survey items.

Table 1

The Reliability of the Scales

Instrument	Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items	Acceptability
Collaborative Practices	0.78	5	Acceptable
Impact of Sustainable Collaboration	0.84	5	Acceptable
Challenges to sustainable collaboration	0.91	5	Acceptable

As shown in Table 1, the Cronbach's Alpha values for all variables exceed 0.7, specifically measuring at 0.86, 0.91, and 0.77. These results suggest that the instrument exhibits satisfactory internal consistency.

3.5. Data analysis

The quantitative data collected from the surveys were analyzed using statistical software. Descriptive statistics were calculated to summarize the responses for each survey item.

3.6. Ethical considerations

This study adhered to ethical guidelines, including obtaining informed consent from all participants. Participation was voluntary, and participants had the right to withdraw at any time. Confidentiality was maintained by anonymizing data and securely storing all collected information.

3.7. Limitations

While this study aimed to provide valuable insights into the challenges of collaboration in Ethiopian private schools, limitations included potential response bias in self-reported data and the generalizability of findings to all private schools in Ethiopia. Additionally, the diverse educational contexts may have resulted in variability in responses that could affect comparative analysis.

4. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Findings

RQ1. What collaborative practices are currently being implemented in Addis Ababa's private schools, and how do they vary among different institutions?

Table 2

Collaborative Practices in Addis Ababa's Private Schools

No	Items	N	Mean	SD
1	Teachers in my school frequently engage in collaborative planning sessions.	350	3.51	0.82
2	My school provides structured professional development opportunities that effectively promote collaboration among teachers.	350	3.64	0.73
3	Peer feedback mechanisms (e.g., peer observations and collaborative teaching) are effective in enhancing teaching practices at my school.	350	3.56	0.88
4	Parents and community members are actively involved in collaborative practices at my school.	350	3.75	0.68
5	The school administration is supportive of fostering a culture of	350	3.58	0.97

collaboration among teachers.				
	Overall Average	350	3.61	0.82

4.1.1 Frequency of collaboration

This is clear from the data offered in the first item in Table 2 where the mean value for teachers' collaborative planning was 3.51. This implies that there is a good work culture in learning institutions where people are expected to work in groups. Practices of this nature should increase instructional quality since adoption of integrated approaches to planning entails sharing of various strategies and resources that has potential to improve students learning. Nonetheless, the standard deviation of 0.82 is an indication that the frequency of teachers' participation in such sessions varies considerably.

It is for this reason that variability of the above findings gives rise to questions that relate to the factors that determine engagement in the collaborative planning process. Although many teachers are likely to be quite engaged and play a big part, there are likely to be many who, for one reason or another, are unable to engage much—for example, because they have too much work to do, or their administrators do not support them. Closing these gaps is important in order to achieve the best collaborative efforts within the school environment. Thus, realizing that some teachers have difficulties in some of these aspects, the school can work towards creating an environment in which all teachers can really profit from collaborative planning and other forms of staff development.

4.1.2. Structured professional development

Self-generated professional learning as captured in item number two of table 2 shows that the school offers professional development opportunities that facilitate teacher collaboration to a moderate extent and moderately so with a mean score of 3.64. That this mean is slightly above in the midpoint signifies that educators believe that such opportunities are useful and effective in creating a collaborative culture. It is such structured programs casting significant importance into play for it provides the teachers with abilities and structures catered to teamwork hence improving the experience of students in education.

With a standard deviation of 0.73, the study shows that there is moderate agreement and consistency in the responses given. It further implies that although the overwhelming majority of the teachers are aware of effectiveness of these professional development opportunities, there may be some discrepancy regarding the experiences. Such fluctuations could be attributed to relative differences in the level of involvement as well as divergent perceptions of the programs' applicability. To enhance collaboration this feedback should be pursued by the school to guarantee that professional development is not only availed but also serves each of the teachers' needs thus deepening absorption of collaborative culture within the school.

4.1.3. Peer feedback mechanisms

It is clear for item number 3 in the Table 2 that peer feedback mechanisms such as peer observation and collaborative teaching are perceived to be effective for improving the teaching practice at the school where the study was carried out with a mean score of 3.56. These findings imply that most teachers embrace such practices because they affirm the importance of such practices in enhancing personal as well as shared professional development. It is essential to have such mechanisms because the idea is to enable the educators to freely discuss and share constructive criticism their ideas that could lead to better performance within classrooms.

Nevertheless, it's seen that the standard deviation of this experiment is 0.88, which educates a lot concerning the range of possible reactions to the utilization of peer feedback, which might signal that the encounter is rather variant for different teachers. While others can get fully involved and maximize on these opportunities there will always be those who may feel uncomfortable or even maybe left out. This is because the school should try and find out more about why there is such a variation in the beliefs held in their institution. By offering extra professional development opportunities and resources and by promoting positive attitudes toward peer feedback in the school, it will be possible to increase teachers' interest in these practices; thus, all teachers will be able to participate in collaborative processes to improve their instruction practices.

4.1.4. Involvement of stakeholders

In the data indicated in Table two item number four of means shows that parents and community members are both engaged in collaborative practice in the school with a mean of 3.75. This an indicator that teachers have a strong perception of partnerships going beyond the classroom but encompassing families and the larger community. It is also important that all stakeholders are involved in the process because not only does it boost the learning process of a particular school, but it also makes the members of the school community serve as responsible supporters of the school's mission.

But reading an average value of 0.68 shows that there is moderate level of consistency in responses which in

turn implies that although many educators realize the benefit of community participation, there can still be variation in the degree or even the type of participation. These perceptions could be therefore affected by the level of parental involvement or community mobilization for example. To extend some of these collaborative practices more effectively, it is recommended that the school should develop other means or strategies of involving parents and other members of the community in the school so that they take full participation of the school activities.

4.1.5. Support from administration

The data in Table two item number 5 reveal that teachers perceive the school administrators as supportive of collaboration with a mean score of 3.58. This score means there is a better perception by educators about the role of the administration in encouraging collaborative processes in the work place. This support is important as people need to feel encouraged to pool their ideas with other teachers, share their planning, and goal setting; this will in turn improve on the extents to which effective teaching and therefore improved results can be produced.

However, the low coefficient of 0.97 shows that the responses are highly dispersed, do not align with the finding that all teachers have high confidence in the administrative support for collaboration. Such differences may depend on the personal use of leadership or the existence and the nature of policies that encourage co-operation in an organization. To this end, the administration should consider engaging the staff so as to make a comparison of the perceptions between them and the administration of the center. In the context of the present study, the administration can facilitate and enhance the collaborative milieu by displaying commitment to collaboration through implementing and promoting specifically geared activities and materials.

RQ2. *How does sustainable collaboration among teachers, administrators, and parents impact the quality of teaching and student engagement in Addis Ababa’s private schools?*

Table 3

The Impact of Sustainable Collaboration on Teaching Quality and Student Engagement

No	Items	N	Mean	SD
1	Sustainable collaboration among teachers, administrators, and parents significantly improves the quality of teaching in my school	350	3.63	0.92
2	Collaborative efforts among teachers and parents lead to increased student engagement in the classroom	350	3.72	0.85
3	The collaboration between teachers, administrators, and parents enhances communication and feedback regarding student performance.	350	3.69	0.78
4	Sustainable collaboration helps create a more supportive learning environment for students in my school.	350	3.45	0.71
5	I believe that sustainable collaboration contributes to the overall success of students in my school.	350	3.71	0.88
Overall Average		350	3.64	0.83

4.1.6. Impact on teaching quality

Table three item number one reveals that sustainable collaboration between teachers’ admins and parents enhance the quality in my school by a mean of 3.63. This indicates that educators still acknowledge the essential work that collaboration brings for enhancing teaching improvement practices, as well as resulting in improved student learning outcomes as mentioned in the previous sections of this paper. This suggests that to nurture the culture for quality education, there is need to undertake organizational transformation that promotes teamwork and shared accountability by all stakeholders.

However, the standard deviation of 0.92 still points to a large dispersion of responses, which helps to conclude that while perceiving the effectiveness of collaboration among staff members, people may have very different opinion. It is quite possible to receive lots of support and participation among teachers, as well as struggle with factors that compromise their participation. To increase effectiveness of these cooperative processes, it is recommended that the school tries to identify the causes for these fluctuations. For that reason, when the school encourages the inclusive communication and offers the resources that will enable every participant to foster a connection, the spirit of collaboration can be advanced further and the general effectiveness of the pedagogy can be enhanced even more.

4.1.7. Enhancement of student engagement

The findings in dimension two, item number two in table 3 show that collective work of teachers and parents is perceived to unlock interest of the students in class with a mean score of 3.72. Furthermore, the high total suggests that teachers understand how important and necessary parental participation and cooperation with faculty are for developing an interesting learning environment. Whenever the parents and teachers bring in their support, it becomes easier for the child to have full support from the two and this usually leads to high degree of motivation as well as actively participating in some activities within the classroom.

A margin of 0.85 means that variability of response is moderate and it is also clear that while many teachers notice positive effects of these collaborations the attitudes or views of the staff vary. It's possible for some educators to believe collaboration increases engagement, while others might face challenges in implementing this strategy: For example, there can be differences in participating parents' involvement or teachers' communication. In this line, the school should pay much attention on cooperation with parents and assure all teachers have necessary equipment and helpful means to collaborate. Through addressing these disparities, the school can develop a coherent strategy of improving learners' participation in the classroom.

4.1.8. Communication and feedback

From Table 3, item number 3 shows that the extent of teachers' administrators and parents' communication and feedback on students' performance has improved, with a mean score of 3.69. Hence this score captures growing agreement that collaborative practices enhance the provision of constructive feedback with regard to student progress. It is about the fact that, when all the interested parties work in unison and convey their respective messages every day, then a more harmonious educational working climate is produced that is most effective when applied to the students.

The low coefficient of variation of 0.78 points to a relative homogeneity of the perception among the respondents in the study to the extent that most of the teachers had a positive perception of the fact that collaboration enhanced effective communication. However, the existence of some variation suggests that possibly a few instructors may not fully participate in these collaborative activities probably as a result of these variations in experience or depth of involvement. Thus, to strengthen the effect of developing good collaboration in improving communication, the school needs to undertake steps to guarantee that everyone is involved and there are set chances for feedback between educators, administrators, and parents. When the school creates an environment that supports this change, it will be easier to develop systems for supporting student performance and bring together all the parties concerned with the issue, to ensure they are all pulling in the same direction.

4.1.9. Supportive learning environment

From table three, item number 4 has a mean score of 3.45, suggesting that sustainable collaboration is believed to enhance the learning environment of student in the school. This score indicates a rather positive perception of the subject and its measure in terms of the positive impact of collaboration; however, it is lower than in previous items, Therefore, there is still potential to enhance the attitudes towards the practices of collaboration based on specific suggestions. It is very important to nurture a positive learning atmosphere in classroom and cooperation between teachers, school staff and parents is one of the most important factors for achieving this.

The value of 0.71 proves the fact that majority of the educators have similar perception about the concept and moderate level of reliability because the results have small variation between them but at the same time do not have absolutely similar ideas about the benefits of collaboration for creating support atmosphere. Some of the reasons may include; the success of current collaborative efforts or maybe levels of contribution ranged from one pillar to the other. To build up the supportive factor of learning environment, the school should indeed improve and increase the collaborative practices across them so that all the member of the educational context seems to be able to make. Thereby improving the overall collaborative culture of the school can greatly help in reaching out in meeting the needs of all students and improve on their overall performance.

4.1.10. Student success

From Table 3, responses relating to item number 5 shows that educators are of the opinion that sustainable collaboration enhance the effectiveness of students in the school with a mean score of 3.71. This score has notified a high level of agreement among teachers concerning the benefits resulting from collaborative initiatives on learners' performance. If teachers, administrators and parents are involved in the process it forms a supportive system that caters for the part development in the child and makes the essence of collaboration to support improved student performance very clear.

This variability is secure by standard deviation of 0.88, which means that though alone there are a lot of educators understood the issue beneficial for collaboration, there could be some who might have different opinions or experiences. Such variations may result from differences in people's perception of how collaboration

is enacted in the school or differences in the level of participation by stakeholders. To further amplify the extent to which sustainable collaboration driving student success can be scaled up, the school ought to consider going an extra step further in admitting and trying to respond to the interests of stakeholders who may otherwise feel detached from sustainability efforts. This way the school may try to improve the overall structure of education in its settings in favor of students since the additional points towards cooperation can contribute to the formation of more united environment.

RQ3. *What are the key challenges and barriers to establishing sustainable collaboration in Addis Ababa's private schools, and how can these be addressed to enhance educational outcomes?*

Table 4

Challenges to establishing sustainable collaboration				
No	Items	N	Mean	SD
1	Cultural attitudes and norms within the school community hinder the establishment of sustainable collaboration among teachers, administrators, and parents.	350	2.23	0.75
2	Insufficient resources (e.g., funding, time, training) present significant challenges to fostering sustainable collaboration in my school.	350	3.32	0.71
3	Poor communication channels among stakeholders impede effective collaboration in my school.	350	2.01	0.93
4	The lack of support from school leadership is a major barrier to establishing sustainable collaboration among staff and parents.	350	1.45	1.23
5	There is a significant need for training and professional development to equip teachers and administrators with the skills necessary for effective collaboration.	350	3.71	0.76
Overall Average		350	2.54	0.88

4.1.11. Cultural barriers

Cultural attitudes and norms in the school community as a factor of sustainable collaboration among teachers, administrators, and parents are not an issue according to data highlighted in Table 4; item number 1=2.23. This low mean implies that educators in the present study hold a relatively less negative perception of the Social Cultural Context by endorsing a view that preexisting cultural processes do not inhibit collaboration. It suggests that there might be a more optimistic view of the prospects for cooperation to unfold within the existing cultural environment.

With SD value of 0.75, it means variability in response is quite high which raises a question of whether there are still some negative cultural norms that staff encounter that do not support collaboration. Thus, there are some educators who will have a more positive attitude towards the cultural climate, while others may still face certain difficulties. I therefore recommend that to supplement the positive sentiment of the respondents, the school should encourage practices that supports the positive cultural aspects established in the study. Having regular, candid conversations on how practitioners can work together and recognizing good practice of integrated work by teachers, administrators, and parents can go a long way in enhancing the relations for more supportive community for sustainable collaboration.

4.1.12. Limited resources

As shown in Table 4, item number 2 shows that lack of resources including, funding, time and training for collaboration are major barriers towards sustainability in the school and attained a mean score of 3.32. In light of this score work, it can be confidently stated that the level of concern of educators concerning the access and asset availability vital to cooperation is moderate. The major drawback that it captures is concern that without sufficiently enhanced supplementary cooperation maybe restricted which in turn affect the teaching and learning process.

The standard deviation of 0.71 proves quite low implying that the respondents' perception is quite high and consistent with the important challenges faced by many educators due to such restrictions in availability of resources. But a little variation means that several teachers may not hold the same opinion, which could be attributed to the number of teachers' experiences on the availability of resources in their practice settings. To overcome these difficulties, the school administration should be strategic in resource distribution providing teachers with enough necessary funding, time for meetings, and professional development. By developing these areas, the school could increase several effective processes and practices that would foster cooperation between

teachers, parents and administrators and provide the best for children.

4.1.13. Communication issues

Data presented in Table 4, item no. 3, reveals that weak communication networks do not negatively affect collaborative working in the school, mean=2.01. Low mean also indicates that educators in general share a positive view on how communication channels are useful and do not hinder interaction. It means that the teaching staff, school leaders, and caregivers believe that their communication is adequate to sustain cooperation.

Therefore, the studies observe a standard deviation of 0.93, a position that confirms a strong and high level of consensus among the respondents on the perception that communication is not a barrier to cooperation within the school community. Yes, maybe there can be certain disparities at this or that, however, the overall perspective for it is positive. Thus, the key recommendation that the school can make for the improvement of cross-functional cooperation is the encouragement of frequent and open communication between all the members of the learning community. Continued feedback and positive participation are good ways to improve these lines of communication at all time, and this can be as a result of working with parents and embracing, the communities that these individuals belong to in the society.

4.1.14. Lack of leadership support

As reflected in Table 4 where item number 4 defines school leadership's unwillingness to support sustainable collaboration among the staff and parents as not being a barrier with a mean score of 1.45. The low mean concerning the school leadership perception indicate that in general educators agree with one another when observing that school leadership is supportive of collaboration. It means teachers and parents have perception that facilitate recognition from their leaders to practice collaborative work.

The standard deviation of 1.23 shows that the responses are quite diverse mainly due to the variation of some staff views regarding the supportive role of leadership while most of them support the view, percentage-wise. A couple of persons may feel that they did not experience many positive leadership outcomes, but on balance, the results show a bias towards positive leadership engagement in promoting collaboration. In order to enhance commitment to such a supportive context, school leadership needs to consciously advocate and demonstrate collaborative processes to increase the sense of purpose and ownership of all actors involved. If done correctly, this can improve the collaborative culture, which will supplement the benefits for the staff and students.

4.1.15. Need for training

Table 4, item number 5 shows that teachers and administrators need training and professional development to prepare them for effective collaboration with an average response of 3.71. This relatively high score indicates that, in the opinion of educators, it is extremely important to constantly develop training in the sphere of increasing collaboration within the stipulated school. It would support ideas that, although various stakeholders are already working together, there are remaining deficiencies in knowledge and skills that might be filled through career development.

The coefficient of 0.76 means there should be moderate level of agreement among the respondents, which signify that although many educators are of the opinion that training is important, there might differ in their opinions regarding the present training. It also revealed that some teachers are more prepared to handle influential ideas than others and therefore there is a need to enhance professional development to address needs of staff members. Therefore, the school should make training programs targeting collaborative skills, develop teamwork and strengthen communication among all stakeholders. Such measures would help the school develop more effective working relations within the faculty and design a new environment that could benefit students and educators as well.

4.2 DISCUSSION

The survey findings highlight several key aspects of the organizational culture surrounding collaboration within the school community. Educators generally express strong confidence in the positive impact of teamwork among teachers, principals, and parents on various facets of learning. This perspective aligns with existing literature that emphasizes the importance of intersectoral collaborations, which have been shown to significantly enhance teaching standards and positively influence student outcomes (e.g., Ramukumba, et al., 2019).

Furthermore, the perceived involvement of parents and community members underscores the notion that partnerships are essential and pervasive. Research supports this view, indicating that when families actively engage in the educational process, students tend to achieve higher levels of success and motivation (Descals-Tomas, et al., 2021). Additionally, effective communication channels among all stakeholders facilitate this collaborative culture by providing essential feedback regarding student performance.

However, the survey also reveals challenges that the school faces in sustaining these collaborative efforts. While cultural attitudes within the school community do not appear to be major barriers, issues such as insufficient resources require attention. The need for adequate funding, time, and training is critical for fostering

partnerships and supporting educators. This finding is particularly significant in light of previous studies that highlight the necessity of professional development in promoting effective collaboration (Kilag, & Sasan, 2023).

Moreover, the high level of positive perception of collaboration among school leadership indicates that leadership plays a pivotal role in fostering these collaborative environments. Effective leadership models can guide the school community toward a more integrated approach to education, reinforcing the findings of Ang'ana, & Kilika, (2022) that suggest strong leadership is a key determinant of successful collaborative practices.

In summary, while the survey underscores the benefits of collaboration and community involvement, it also points to important areas for improvement, particularly regarding resource allocation and leadership development. Addressing these challenges will be essential for enhancing the collaborative culture within the school community.

5. CONCLUSION

An important finding of the present survey is a strong awareness of shared responsibility for collaboration amongst teachers, administrators and parents within the school context. Teachers understand the huge advantages of interdependent activities and acknowledge the availability of these approaches in terms of teaching efficacy, learners' appeal, and educational outcomes. Scholars say both parents' engagement and communication among the stakeholders complement this culture of collaboration and extend support to students' learning processes.

Nevertheless, it is possible to identify key areas of concern such as utilization of resources, and staff development. These challenges must be met if collaborative efforts are going to be sustained and strengthened into the future. The school can then improve its teamwork collaboration by providing training and making sure that educators have all the training resources that are needed.

Lastly, creating collaboration culture not only enhance the professional practice of teachers and administrators, but it also greatly enhances the student's experience. Further work in fostering support from all providers and stakeholders involved in education will also remain critical in delivering sustained and positive reform changes for the students and development of a successful learning climate for every learner.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the survey, several recommendations can be made to enhance collaborative practices within the school community:

1) **Increase Resource Allocation:** With regard to the above challenges of inadequate resources, the school needs to provide more funding, time and materials toward collaborative activities. This might involve the use of accommodation for collaboration and interaction such as technology equipment's of communication and planning.

2) **Enhance Professional Development:** Design specific, intensive continuing training sessions that address such vital aspects as teaming and teamwork along with interpersonal communication. Such programs should cover a broad range of staff needs in the teaching and administrative arena so that all employees include teachers and administration understands and possesses the appropriate skills for collaboration.

3) **Strengthen Communication Channels:** As with any form of communication currently in existent, there is always the tendency to want more as a mode of communication. Such changes include organizing daily and weekly teachers, administrators, and parents' meetings, forums, and workshops. This will help to strengthen relationship and guarantee feedback is being offered at the right time.

4) **Conduct Regular Assessments:** Conduct audits as often as possible for collaborative processes and the resource availability to the educators. Getting information from the teachers, school officials and the parents you get a good base of what can be improved and how the school should change its strategies.

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